

Explaining a rainbow bridge warp drive.

This is a true compass:

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This is a quantum rainbow arc (bottom of the rainbow) magneto prism that has binary duality if used as a needle pointer.

This is a group of quantum magneto weirdness orbs with quite a lot of force:

Together, the quantum rainbow magneto prisms and the quantum magneto weirdness orbs can be combined and turned in to a truest compass as long as a true compass is placed in the middle to tell true north. The true compass points north, and then a magneto prism pointer is placed where the north points, where the truest north may point in a different direction, and especially with these needles there is a binary opposite duality of directions.

Depending on if the quantum rainbow magneto prism pointers are placed inside or outside of the magneto orb ring, depends on if it is north within the horizon of the map currently being scouted or beyond the horizon of the map currently being scouted. Same can be applied for other directions. Magneto prism pointers be combined to create a false compass, where if two magneto prism pointers are combined in to 1 pointer, it creates a false direction, three pointers and it's a falser direction, and five pointers for a falsest direction.

In essence, this truest quantum compass uses a gravitational field and a rainbow arc to tell where the truest directions of the land are.

Possibly, if a map is created, it may be able to be set in stone, and through macro fusion, the map may change eventually.

And so, to explain how to observe the rainbow bridge warp drive as the quantum observer, first this image is explained, where first a twice folded then flipped then folded again thinking paper with a thinking note that is written on that folder paper that is placed inside the warp drive. Then a true north rainbow magneto prism needle is placed inside the center of the ring.

Then, first, the north needle is placed where true north is pointing, then east is placed parallel to the north needle, then the west needle is placed symmetrically to the east needle, then the south needle is placed parallel to the west needle.

Therefore, to observe this warp drive, it is true north that is brought within the horizon of the north facing needle. The north needle has a fade black north edge. The east needle is a golden reflective south facing edge. The west needle is pointing at inactive up. South is outside light clone gold fade.

To explain a fully observed rainbow bridge warp drive, first I start with the note I wrote that I placed in the middle of the warp drive, to explain the location of the compass log, where the thinking note goes as followed: The mirrored image of the components of my rainbow bridge warp drive location. Then, here I will explain my compass log: True north that is pointed at dulled golden outside light middle. Within the horizon of the mirrored image of the components of my rainbow bridge warp drive location: North that is pointed at outside light bottomless trench ocean that becomes a sea middled edge. East that is pointed at a contradiction that became dawn then sunset outside light. West that is pointed up with a golden tip that when the tip is looked at the gold fades away that is pulled within the horizon of true north. South is a rainbow bridge pulled north east within the horzion of true north. Beyond the horzion of the mirrored image of the components of my rainbow bridge warp drive location: North that is pointed with a golden edge that changes to a silver edge that changes to a golden edge with a deep blue ocean tip pulled within the horizon. East at complete outside light with slight rainbow bridge mirror image, dawned, pulled within the horizon. West at a grey tipped

middle edge with an ultra violet middle outer that joins to a black edge, pulled towards and in to the horizon yet remains slightly beyond the horizon. South with no duality with a deep ultra violet tip pointing away from the horizon within that fades away and tipped outside light dark matter middle that changes to blue matter middle that changes to dark matter middle which produces the result of a fade space warp and also tipped with an unexplainable colour that is pulled within the horizon. Dated as the 17th day of the 5th month of the 2025th year.